
Preparatory measurements for a direct laser excitation of $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$

Nicolas Arlt

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**Vorbereitende Messungen für eine
direkte Laseranregung des Isomers
 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$**

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Nicolas Arlt

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Abstract

^{229m}Th is an exotic nuclear isomeric state, providing the lowest known nuclear excitation energy of 7.8 ± 0.5 eV. For this reason ^{229m}Th promises interesting applications in a potential field of nuclear quantum optics. In order to get complete optical access to ^{229m}Th it is, however, essential to determine the isomeric energy up to an uncertainty of ± 0.1 eV or better. For this purpose a magnetic-bottle retarding field electron spectrometer has been characterized. With this device a determination of the isomeric energy via a direct nuclear laser excitation scheme is envisaged. In this concept, a magnetic-bottle is used to guide the internal conversion electrons, as emitted during the isomeric decay of ^{229m}Th , towards a microchannel plate detector. In order to obtain the highest probability for the detection of internal conversion electrons, following the direct laser excitation of the isomeric state, significant effort was spent on the understanding and suppression of background signals. A large amount of background signals in the form of photoelectrons emerges from the irradiated sample surface and the inside of the spectrometer body as a consequence of the laser irradiation. These can be influenced and even partly be removed by voltages assigned to the sample and setup-inserted grids. A sufficient suppression of background electrons has eventually been accomplished by a triggered sample voltage and most likely paves the way for a successful laser excitation and energy measurement of ^{229m}Th .

Zusammenfassung

^{229m}Th ist ein exotischer isomerer Kernzustand, der die niedrigste bekannte Kernanregungsenergie von 7.8 ± 0.5 eV besitzt. Aus diesem Grund verspricht ^{229m}Th interessante Anwendungen in einem potentiellen Feld der "nuklearen Quantenoptik". Um einen vollständigen optischen Zugang zu ^{229m}Th zu bekommen ist es jedoch essentiell, die Isomerenergie bis auf eine Unsicherheit von ± 0.1 eV oder besser zu bestimmen. Aus diesem Grund wurde im Rahmen dieser Bachelorarbeit ein magnetisches Flaschen-Elektronenspektrometer charakterisiert. Mithilfe dieser Vorrichtung ist eine Bestimmung der Isomerenergie mittels einer direkten Laseranregung vorgesehen. Im Rahmen dieses Konzepts wird eine magnetische Flasche benutzt, um die Elektronen, die beim "inneren Konversionszerfall" des Isomers entstehen, auf einen MCP-Detektor zu lenken. Um die höchstmögliche Wahrscheinlichkeit für die Detektion der Konversionselektronen nach einer erfolgreichen Laseranregung zu erlangen,

wurde viel Arbeit in das Verständnis und das Unterdrücken von Untergrundelektronen investiert. Der Hauptteil der Untergrundelektronen entsteht durch Photoemission der laserbestrahlten Oberflächen im Inneren des Spektrometers. Diese können durch Spannungen auf der Sampleoberfläche und auf Gittern im Spektrometer beeinflusst und sogar teilweise unterdrückt werden. Eine ausreichende Reduktion der Untergrundelektronen wurde letztendlich durch eine getriggerte Samplespannung erreicht und ebnet damit höchstwahrscheinlich den Pfad für eine erfolgreiche Laseranregung und Energiemessung von $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$.

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1 Introduction and Motivation

Within the broad spectrum of atomic physics, light-matter-interaction has played a central role ever since. Particularly electron transitions between the energy levels within the atomic shell, at which electrons absorb suitable photon energies corresponding to the relevant transitions, subsequently excite into energetically higher states and eventually emit photons with a characteristic energy, provide lots of applications in the fields of quantum optics, e.g., a huge variety of lasers or highly precise clocks. Their transition energies typically lie in the range of some electronvolts, easy to obtain by, e.g., visible light. Optical atomic clocks are the most precise clocks existing these days and used as frequency standards. They have brought incredible advances in time and frequency metrology, performing up to an uncertainty of 2×10^{-18} [1].

Similar to the atomic shell, also atomic nuclei possess excited states. Here characteristic energies lie in the range of at least a few keV, which is why an optical excitation of these states is difficult to realize. In principle, however, it would be possible to try transferring knowledge of light-shell interaction to a nuclear system, leading to promising applications such as a nuclear clock [2, 3], a nuclear laser [4] or nuclear quantum optics in general [5]. Fortunately, nature has provided one particular nuclear excited state of exceptionally low energy, which is the metastable state in ^{229}Th (denoted as $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$), providing an energy of only 7.8 eV. This nuclear state is in reach of already existing laser technology and could therefore serve as a first candidate for the development of a nuclear clock (Fig. 1.1). A potential nuclear clock based on $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ is predicted to reach a fractional frequency uncertainty of up to 1×10^{-19} , due to an expected high stability against external influences like electromagnetic fields [3]. This twenty times higher accuracy could lead to the development of a new, nuclear based frequency standard [2, 3].

Already in 1976, the nucleus of ^{229}Th was predicted to possess an isomeric (metastable) state with an excitation energy below 100 eV [7]. In 1994, the transition energy was constrained to 3.5 ± 1.0 eV, being the most accepted value for a long time [8]. In 2007, however, a corrected energy value of 7.8 ± 0.5 eV was published, based on a measurement using a magnetic microcalorimeter providing an energy resolution of 30 eV [9, 10]. This extraordinary low

Figure 1.1: Energy-half-life distribution of nuclear isomers (blue circles) including $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ and several atomic shell transitions (indicated by the red circles in the orange colored area) [6].

nuclear excitation energy does conceptually allow for a direct laser excitation and the development of a $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ -based nuclear clock. For the development of a clock based on single ^{229}Th ions, as proposed in [2, 3], it is, however, essential to determine the transition energy more precisely.

Recently, a new way for the determination of the isomeric energy was proposed, making use of direct $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ laser excitation in a solid ^{229}Th sample [11]. A layer of ^{229}Th is laser irradiated and, in case of resonance, it is expected that a significant number of nuclei will be excited into the isomeric state.

The dominating decay channel of $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ in the neutral atom is via internal conversion (IC) under emission of an electron from the valence shell of ^{229}Th . The corresponding branching ratio is about 10^9 and the IC decay channel was recently used for the direct detection of the isomeric decay [6]. Under this condition, the half-life of $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ was measured to be $7 \pm 1 \mu\text{s}$ [12].

As the isomeric lifetime is significantly longer than an individual laser pulse of a few ns duration used for sample irradiation, it is the conceptual idea to probe the nuclear excitation via the IC electrons as expectedly emitted from the sample after the end of each laser pulse. A magnetic-bottle spectrometer was designed to guide the IC electrons to a microchannel-plate detector in order to probe the isomeric deexcitation. In this way, the IC detection

is spatially decoupled from the radioactive ^{229}Th sample and background in form of high-energy particles from the radioactive decay is suppressed.

In this concept, photoelectrons, that emerge as a result of the laser pulse, will pose a major source of background. Typically, these electrons will only be emitted during the laser irradiation. However, time-of-flight effects may eventually lead to a propagation of the photoelectron background signal. It is a central aspect of this thesis to test if it is possible to suppress the photoelectronic background by correspondingly chosen electric fields in a way that would allow for the detection of IC electrons with $7 \mu\text{s}$ half-life in coincidence with each laser pulse. The transition energy can then be derived from the wavelength and the linewidth of the laser used for the excitation.

In the case of success, the direct excitation of an isomeric nuclear state and all subsequent potential applications will bring a tremendous breakthrough in nuclear physics and eventually result in the expansion of the field of quantum optics to a nuclear level.

2 Theoretical background

This chapter gives a theoretical overview on the physical principles that are used throughout this thesis. At first, the dominating decay channel of neutral ^{229m}Th , internal conversion, is described. As it is envisaged to measure electrons in a magnetic bottle spectrometer, the behaviour of charged particles in electric and magnetic fields is described in the subsequent section. The last section then describes a direct laser excitation scheme of ^{229m}Th .

2.1 Internal Conversion

Nuclei possess excited states, which can decay to their ground state or to neighbouring excited states via several decay channels. One of these decay channels is internal conversion (IC), which is described in the following section. The resulting charged particle one obtains after IC decay is an electron originating from the atomic shell. The process is shown in the Feynman diagram in Fig. 2.1. The IC decay results from an interaction between the excited state of the nucleus and the atomic shell. Since the wave functions of the shell electrons and the nucleus overlap (in particular for s-electrons), the shell electrons have a finite probability of presence within the nucleus. A prerequisite for internal conversion is, that the transition energy E_γ is larger than the binding energy of the electron E_X which is emitted:

$$E_\gamma > E_X. \quad (2.1)$$

The resulting conversion electron has then a kinetic energy of

$$E = E_\gamma - E_X. \quad (2.2)$$

The electron's kinetic energy will therefore allow to determine the transition energy.

Figure 2.1: Feynman diagram of the IC decay: The excited nucleus X^* interacts with an electron bound in an atomic shell e_b . The resulting particles are the deexcited ion X^+ and a conversion electron, e_{IC} , which can be detected.

2.1.1 Internal Conversion and ^{229m}Th

Usually, IC decay occurs for electrons in the lowest shells, since the probability of presence within the nucleus is higher for these. However, in the case of ^{229m}Th , the emitted electron originates from the valence shell, which is due to the low excitation energy of only about 7.8 eV: the first ionization potential of ^{229}Th is 6.31 eV and therefore, in the case of neutral ^{229m}Th , Eq. (2.1) is fulfilled and the isomer decays via IC. The situation drastically changes already in the case of singly charged ^{229m}Th ions, since the second ionization potential of ~ 12 eV exceeds the expected isomeric energy and thus IC is forbidden [13].

2.2 Charged particles in magnetic fields

In this section, the motion of charged particles within electromagnetic fields is described. In particular, the principle of the magnetic mirror will be discussed. The derivations in Sect. 2.2.1 until Sect. 2.2.3 follow Ref. [14].

2.2.1 Homogeneous fields and influence of an external force

In the following, particles with mass m and charge q , which are moving with velocity \mathbf{v} in a homogeneous and time-independent magnetic field \mathbf{B} will be considered. Additionally, a constant, external force \mathbf{F} shall affect the particles. Hence, the particles fulfill Newton's equation of motion

$$m\dot{\mathbf{v}} = q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{F}. \quad (2.3)$$

Assuming $\mathbf{B} = B\mathbf{e}_z$, the following differential equations hold for accelerations \dot{v}_x , \dot{v}_y and \dot{v}_z :

$$\dot{v}_x = +\frac{qB}{m}v_y + \frac{F_x}{m} \quad (2.4)$$

$$\dot{v}_y = -\frac{qB}{m}v_x + \frac{F_y}{m} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\dot{v}_z = +\frac{F_z}{m}. \quad (2.6)$$

One can easily see, that the equation describing the motion parallel to the magnetic field (Eq. (2.6)) is not affected by \mathbf{B} and leads to the following equation of motion:

$$z(t) = z_0 + v_{0z}t + \frac{F_z}{2m}t^2, \quad (2.7)$$

which is obtained by integration of Eq. (2.6). A force accelerating ions and electrons within the spectrometer parallel to the magnetic field can be realized by applying an electric field gradient, realized by several grids set to different voltages. A more specific description will follow in Sect. 3.

Inserting the time derivative of Eq. (2.4) in Eq. (2.5) decouples the differential equations and provides

$$\ddot{v}_x = -\left(\frac{qB}{m}\right)^2 v_x + \frac{qB}{m^2}F_y \quad (2.8)$$

and

$$\ddot{v}_y = -\left(\frac{qB}{m}\right)^2 v_y - \frac{qB}{m^2}F_x. \quad (2.9)$$

In the case of a vanishing external force ($\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{0}$), Eqs. (2.8) and (2.9) satisfy the differential equation of the classical harmonic oscillator, with the angular frequency $\omega_G = \frac{qB}{m}$, which is called *gyrofrequency*. If $\mathbf{F} \neq \mathbf{0}$, Eqs. (2.8) and (2.9) show that the magnetic field redirects an external force \mathbf{F} 's impact in the direction perpendicular to \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{F} . Introducing the initial condition $\mathbf{v}(t = 0) = v_\perp \mathbf{e}_x$ helps solving the homogeneous part of Eqs. (2.8) and (2.9). One finds, that the particles, with $v_\perp = \sqrt{v_x^2 + v_y^2}$, move on circular paths with following

velocities and equations of motion:

$$v_x = +v_{\perp} \cos \omega_G t \quad (2.10)$$

$$v_y = -v_{\perp} \sin \omega_G t \quad (2.11)$$

and

$$x(t) - x_0 = \frac{v_{\perp}}{\omega_G} \sin \omega_G t \quad (2.12)$$

$$y(t) - y_0 = \frac{v_{\perp}}{\omega_G} \cos \omega_G t. \quad (2.13)$$

The so called *gyroradius* of the circular paths, on which the particles move (also called *Larmor radius*) is then given by

$$\rho_L = \left| \frac{v_{\perp}}{\omega_G} \right| = \left| \frac{mv_{\perp}}{qB} \right|. \quad (2.14)$$

The direction of rotation is then counterclockwise for electrons and clockwise for positive ions, under the assumption that the magnetic field lines are pointing out of the plane.

2.2.2 Inhomogeneous magnetic field

So far, a homogeneous magnetic field has been considered. The motion parallel to the magnetic field then is identical to the case $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{0}$. As will be shown in this section, variations in the field strength may be able to reflect charged particles. In Fig. 2.2 an array of magnetic field lines in z direction is shown. The increasing field lines density corresponds to the increasing field strength. In cylindrical coordinates, the magnetic field can be written in the form $\mathbf{B} = (B_r, 0, B_z)$. We now consider fields where $|B_r| \ll |B_z|$. In case of the magnetic field shown in Fig. 2.2, the magnetic field strength decreases for increasing curvature radii of the electrons. This gradient coupled with the bending of the field lines leads to an azimuthal θ -drift around the symmetry axis, with positive θ -direction for electrons, as illustrated in Fig. 2.2. Due to $B_{\theta} = 0$, no radial drift of the particles is expected. Gauss's law for magnetism states that the divergence of the magnetic field is equal to zero:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r}(rB_r) + \frac{\partial B_z}{\partial z} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.15)$$

Solving Eq. (2.15) for B_r yields that the field's radial component depends on the change of

Figure 2.2: Top: field lines of a magnetic mirror with gyration and precession of the electrons. B_0 and B_m correspond to B_0 and B_{max} from Sect. 2.2.4, determining the capturing condition (see Eq. (2.29)). Bottom: axial component of the inhomogeneous magnetic field, rising from B_0 to B_m [14].

the field strength in axial direction:

$$B_r(r, z) = -\frac{1}{r} \int_0^r dr' r' \frac{\partial B_z(r', z)}{\partial z} \approx -\frac{r}{2} \frac{\partial B_z}{\partial z}. \quad (2.16)$$

Above approximation holds for the magnetic field close to the symmetry axis, as here the gradient of $B_z(r)$ changes slowly in r compared to r itself. Thus the result can be approximated by the product of the gradient and the integral over r .

If the center of a particle's gyromotion is at $r = 0$ and thus the particle is located one gyroradius apart from the axis, the particle experiences a Lorentz force in z direction and the equation of motion parallel to the magnetic field reads:

$$m\dot{v}_z = -qv_\theta B_r = qv_\theta \frac{r}{2} \frac{\partial B_z}{\partial z} = -|qv_\theta| \frac{r}{2} \frac{\partial B_z}{\partial z}. \quad (2.17)$$

The sign is charge-independent, as for positively charged particles, q is positive and v_θ is negative, and vice versa for negatively charged particles. Using (2.14) and $v_\theta = v_\perp$ gives

$$m\dot{v}_z = -\frac{mv_\perp^2}{2B} \frac{\partial B_z}{\partial z}. \quad (2.18)$$

Figure 2.3: Gyration electron considered as current confining a magnetic field with gradient parallel to the magnetic field [14].

This shows, that the magnetic field's inhomogeneity creates a force, which is directed opposite to the magnetic field gradient. Thus, particles on their way in z direction are decelerated and can even be reflected, for $v_{\parallel}(t = 0)$ being not too large. This effect is called *magnetic mirror*. The quantity $\mu = \frac{mv_{\perp}^2}{2B}$ is called *magnetic moment* and is conserved, as will be shown in Sect. 2.2.3.

2.2.3 Conservation of energy and first adiabatic invariant

To ensure conservation of the kinetic energy, v_{\perp} has to change opposed to v_{\parallel} , as results from *Faraday's law of induction*

$$\oint_{\partial A} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{l} = -\frac{d}{dt} \int_A \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{A}. \quad (2.19)$$

It connects the integral of the electric field within a conductor ∂A with the variation of the magnetic flux through the area A , confined by the conductor. Applying Eq. (2.19) on a gyrating electron as shown in Fig. 2.3, the *Larmor radius* ρ_L defines both the area and the perimeter confined by the electron, assuming the perimeter being the infinitely narrow conductor. For a not explicitly time-independent magnetic field one obtains:

$$2\pi\rho_L E_{\theta} = -\pi\rho_L^2 \frac{dB}{dt} = -\pi\rho_L^2 (\nabla_{\parallel} B)v_{\parallel}. \quad (2.20)$$

Although the magnetic field is not explicitly time-independent, the magnetic field experienced by the particle still changes. The resulting force on the electron originating from the induced electric field has then the form

$$m\dot{v}_\theta = m\dot{v}_\perp = -eE_\theta = \frac{1}{2}mv_\perp v_\parallel \frac{\nabla_\parallel B}{B} \quad (2.21)$$

where Eq. (2.14) and the fact that $q = -e$ were used. As v_\parallel decreases, the electric field accelerates the perpendicular motion. In Eq. (2.20) the *Larmor radius* has been assumed to be constant. For changing B and v_\perp , ρ_L will obviously change too. Reorganizing Eq. (2.21) and inserting $v_\parallel \nabla_\parallel B = \frac{dB}{dt}$ leads to

$$\frac{\dot{v}_\perp}{v_\perp} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\dot{B}}{B}, \quad (2.22)$$

which will be needed to show that μ is invariant. The total kinetic energy is given by

$$E_{kin} = \frac{m}{2}(v_\perp^2 + v_\parallel^2). \quad (2.23)$$

To prove energy conservation, the time derivative has to vanish. It is evident that for small *Larmor radii* and $v_\parallel = v_z$ from Eq. (2.18)

$$\dot{E}_{kin} = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{1}{2} m(v_\perp^2 + v_\parallel^2) = m(v_\perp \dot{v}_\perp + v_\parallel \dot{v}_\parallel) = mv_\perp v_\parallel \left(\frac{\dot{v}_\perp}{v_\perp} + \frac{\dot{v}_\parallel}{v_\parallel} \right). \quad (2.24)$$

Inserting Eqs. (2.18) and (2.21) into the above Eq. (2.24) leads to

$$\dot{E}_{kin} = mv_\perp v_\parallel (v_\perp - v_\perp) \frac{\nabla_\parallel B}{2B} = 0, \quad (2.25)$$

which validates energy conservation. Forming the time derivative of the magnetic moment and using Eq. (2.22) yields

$$\dot{\mu} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{mv_\perp^2}{2B} \right) = \frac{mv_\perp \dot{v}_\perp}{B} - \frac{mv_\perp^2}{2B} \frac{dB}{dt} = \mu \left(2 \frac{\dot{v}_\perp}{v_\perp} - \frac{\dot{B}}{B} \right) = 0. \quad (2.26)$$

This proves, that μ is a conserved quantity in magnetic fields, which only depends weakly on the spatial coordinates. The magnetic moment is called *first adiabatic invariant* in this case.

2.2.4 Particles in a magnetic bottle

The inhomogeneous magnetic field described above is called magnetic mirror, since the field lines allow to reflect charged particles under certain conditions. Mirroring the field lines in the x-y-plane leads to a so called magnetic bottle, in which particles can be confined¹. The confinement or reflection of these particles is only realized under certain conditions, which will be derived in the following. A *pitch angle* can be defined by the relation $\tan \alpha = \frac{v_{\perp}}{v_{\parallel}}$. The magnetic moment as a function of α then reads as

$$\mu = \frac{mv^2 \sin^2 \alpha}{2B} = E_{kin} \frac{\sin^2 \alpha}{B} = \text{const.} \quad (2.27)$$

As both μ and E_{kin} are conserved quantities, also $\frac{\sin^2 \alpha}{B} = \text{const.}$ has to hold. Using that at the reflection point $v_{\parallel} = 0$, thus $\alpha = \pi/2$, and assuming that the magnetic field is at the maximum at this point, one obtains:

$$\frac{\sin^2 \alpha}{\sin^2 \frac{\pi}{2}} = \sin^2 \alpha = \frac{B}{B_{max}}. \quad (2.28)$$

Particles at the minimum of the magnetic field B_0 are confined within the magnetic mirror, if the following *capturing condition* for the *pitch angle* applies:

$$\sin \alpha > \sin \alpha_0 = \sqrt{\frac{B_0}{B_{max}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{R_{mirror}}} \quad (2.29)$$

$R_{mirror} = \frac{B_{max}}{B_0}$ is the largest feasible ratio of two values of the magnetic field strength within the magnetic mirror. This means that Eq. (2.29) cannot be satisfied with an initial *pitch angle* $\alpha < \alpha_0$ and that these particles cannot be confined or reflected.

2.3 Direct nuclear laser excitation

A prerequisite for a nuclear optical clock based on thorium is the direct laser excitation of the first isomeric excited state in ²²⁹Th.

So far, this has been hindered by the large uncertainty in the energy value, as it leads to unreasonably long measurement times, when the γ decay of the isomer is employed as a probe

¹For the sake of completeness it must be stated, that the magnetic bottle spectrometer should actually be called magnetic mirror spectrometer, as there is only one magnetic mirror and the particles are not confined, but only reflected.

Figure 2.4: During laser irradiation (red), $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ isomer excitation occurs (blue). After the pulse, IC decay leads to an exponential signal decrease (blue).

for the excitation. The short lifetime of the $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ IC decay channel of $\sim 10 \mu\text{s}$ compared to a theoretically predicted γ -decay lifetime of $\sim 10^4 \text{ s}$ principally gives the opportunity to scan through the $\pm 0.5 \text{ eV}$ uncertainty of the transition energy (corresponding to a bandwidth of $2.4 \times 10^{14} \text{ Hz}$) within a decent time range of about three days by means of a tunable VUV-laser [11]. Fig. 2.4 qualitatively shows the $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ internal conversion activity (blue excitation and decay curve) during and after laser excitation (indicated by the red pulse), for a laser pulse of $3 \mu\text{s}$ duration.

It can be shown, that the number N_{exc} of excited nuclei during the time of laser irradiation t_{exc} obeys the following equation [11]:

$$N_{exc} = \frac{\rho^\omega N_0 \pi^2 c^3}{(1 + \alpha_{IC}) \hbar \omega^3} \frac{g_e}{g_g} (1 - \exp^{-\Gamma_{tot} t_{exc}}), \quad (2.30)$$

with $\Gamma_{tot} = \frac{1}{\tau}$ being the total transition rate of the nuclear excitation (τ is the lifetime of the IC decay), N_0 is the number of irradiated thorium nuclei, ρ^ω is the spectral energy density of the laser, $g_e = \frac{3}{2}$ and $g_g = \frac{5}{2}$ are the degeneracies of the excited and the ground state of ^{229}Th and ω is the angular frequency corresponding to the nuclear transition [11]. For short irradiation durations, Taylor expanding Eq. (2.30) yields

$$(1 - \exp^{-\Gamma_{tot} t_{exc}}) \approx \Gamma_{tot} t_{exc} + \mathcal{O}((\Gamma_{tot} t_{exc})^2), \quad (2.31)$$

Experimentally, such a direct nuclear laser excitation can be achieved by focusing a pulsed laser on a surface that is coated with a monolayer of ^{229}Th . Calculations show, that in such a setup and with nowadays available laser technology (a pulsed VUV-laser system with $10 \mu\text{J}$ pulse energy, 5 ns pulse length and a bandwidth of 10 GHz), ~ 4200 nuclei can be excited

to the isomeric state per pulse. It is, however, expected, that such laser pulses generate background signals, mostly in the form of photoelectrons [11].

3 Experimental Setup

It is the experimental objective of this thesis to test a setup, designed to probe the direct laser excitation of the ^{229}Th nuclear isomer [11]. In this experimental concept, $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ will be excited with a pulsed laser system, irradiating a metallic ^{229}Th sample of 1 mm^2 area and 2 nm thickness. Under these conditions, $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ will predominantly decay via internal conversion under emission of a low-energy electron with a half-life of $7\ \mu\text{s}$, following each individual laser pulse. It is expected, that up to 4200 electrons per pulse will be emitted from the sample, following the isomeric deexcitation [11]. These electrons will be guided by a magnetic-bottle spectrometer towards a microchannel-plate detector.

For the test measurement, the radioactive ^{229}Th target surface is substituted by an aluminum sample and the tunable and pulsed VUV laser system, required for the isomer's excitation, will be exchanged by a 157 nm excimer laser. A sketch of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 3.1.

The central point of the experimental setup is a magnetic-bottle spectrometer. In this magnetic-bottle spectrometer, electrons are emitted from a metallic sample after irradiation with the VUV excimer laser. These electrons are then collected in a strong, inhomogeneous magnetic field and guided into a weak and homogeneous field towards the electron detector. Within the magnetic bottle, electrons can be manipulated with electric fields. In the following sections each component is detailed in order to give a complete description of the experimental setup. At first the magnetic fields are described. Afterwards, the generation of the electric fields, as well as the detection system and the excimer laser are introduced. In a final section the mechanical design and vacuum generation is detailed.

3.1 Magnetic fields

A central component of the magnetic bottle spectrometer is a magnetic mirror, which turns the electrons towards the direction of the MCP detector. To realize the magnetic mirror, one requires two main ingredients: (i) a strong and inhomogeneous magnetic field and (ii) a weak

Figure 3.1: Scheme of the experimental setup developed to probe the laser excitation of $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$.

and homogeneous magnetic field. The strong magnetic field is generated by a permanent magnet described in the subsequent section. The weak magnetic field is obtained by a coil detailed in Sect. 3.1.2.

3.1.1 Magnetic field of the permanent magnet

For the realization of the magnetic mirror, a *VACODYM 772 HR* permanent magnet was used, manufactured by *VACUUMSCHMELZE* [15]. It was positioned in a central position, 32 mm below the entrance of the coil. Therefore it was mounted directly on an optical post, which is fixed to a base plate (detailed in Sect. 3.6). The magnetic field of the permanent magnet was measured (red curve), exhibiting a strong magnetic field strength, close above the permanent magnet, leading to results shown in Fig. 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Logarithmic plot of the magnetic field of the permanent magnet (red curve), measured above the center of the *VACODYM 772 HR*. The sample (see Sect. 3.2.1) is placed between 0.5 and 1 cm over the center of the permanent magnet, according the reference lines (blue).

3.1.2 Magnetic field of the coil

The magnet coil consists of 1.2 mm diameter capton-isolated copper wire coiled onto a hollow aluminum cylinder of 400 mm length and 10 cm outer diameter (see Fig. 3.3). A winding number of $N = 328$ was realized. The magnetic field strength of the coil was measured by means of a Hall probe (Model: *LakeShore MSA-2204-410*). The measurements with a current $I = 2.0$ A are shown in Figs. 3.4 and 3.5.

Fig. 3.4 (a) shows a measurement of the magnetic field along the central axis. It is clearly visible that the magnetic field is homogeneous between 10 and 30 cm inside the coil. Fig. 3.4 (b) shows the magnetic field measured in radial direction in the center (20 cm inside the coil). Taking the error margins into account, the magnetic field strength can be assumed to be constant at varying distances from the central axis. For an infinite coil, the magnetic field is proportional to the current flux through the wire ($B = \mu_0 n I$, μ_0 : vacuum permeability, n : windings per coil length)[16]. As our coil is slim and long enough, its magnetic field in the center is approximated by the magnetic field of an infinite coil. A suitable measurement was conducted and the result in Fig. 3.5 shows a linear dependency between the current and the magnetic field according to the expectation. For $N = 328$ windings and a current $I = 2.0$ A, a magnetic field strength of

$$B = \mu_0 \frac{N}{L} I = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \frac{\text{Vs}}{\text{Am}} \times \frac{328}{0.393\text{m}} \times 2.0\text{A} \simeq 2.1 \times 10^{-3}\text{T} \quad (3.1)$$

Figure 3.3: Body of the coil mounted on the zero length reducer flange, including two electrical feedthroughs (see. Sect. 3.6).

can be calculated for a coil length $L = 393$ mm, which is in good agreement with the measured field strength in the center of the coil, that was measured to be 2.00 ± 0.01 mT.

The decreasing field strength at both ends of the coil is not relevant for the magnetic mirror configuration, as the strong magnetic field provided by the permanent magnet compensates the weak magnetic field at the lower entrance side of the spectrometer (see Fig. 3.6). At the upper end of the coil, the detector is located ~ 10 cm within the coil's body, therefore the decreasing field strength above the detector will not influence the trajectories of the electrons. The resulting magnetic field of both, the coil and the magnet can be plotted by adding both the magnetic field of the coil and the permanent magnet on a logarithmic scale as depicted in Fig. 3.6.

Figure 3.4: (a) Magnetic field measured along the middle axis of the magnetic coil. The distance is measured from the bottom end of the coil. (b) Magnetic field measured along radial direction. Current applied to the coil: $I = 2.0$ A at a voltage $U = 5.2$ V.

Figure 3.5: Magnetic field at the center of the coil at varying currents applied to the coil.

Figure 3.6: Magnetic fields of the permanent magnet and the coil (red) and their superposition (blue) on a logarithmic scale.

3.2 Electric fields

3.2.1 Sample

An aluminum sample serves as probing surface to generate photoelectrons by laser irradiation. A voltage can be set to influence the emerging electrons by means of a *mesytec MHV-4* voltage supply [17]. The sample is mounted to a tip-tilt mirror holder, which is fixed on a base plate in the vacuum chamber (see Sect. 3.6). For the direct laser excitation, a gold surface would be coated with a thin layer of metallic ^{229}Th , replacing the aluminum sample [11]. For a retarding field spectroscopy, the $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ ions would be collected on the sample surface, where they would then neutralize and decay predominantly via internal conversion.

3.2.2 Grids

In order to manipulate the electrons emerging on the sample with electric fields, two different electrode arrangements are used: A first, rather simple setup uses two copper grids (see. Fig.

Figure 3.7: (a) Permanent magnet below the sample area, MgF_2 -lense and bottom coil entrance with lower grid. (b) Upper grid fixed in front of the MCP with black pasteboard aperture covering the gap from electrons.

3.8 (a)). Here one grid is mounted directly in front of the MCP detector (*grid 1*, see Fig. 3.7 (b)). The other grid is mounted to the bottom entrance of the coil (*grid 2*, see Fig. 3.7 (a)). Voltages are applied via the *mesytec MHV-4* voltage supply.

In order to obtain a more dedicated setup, the original setup described above was slightly modified. *Grid 1* was swapped against a more complicated construction, consisting of 10 ring electrodes arranged along the axis of the coil (see Fig. 3.8 (b)). The electric potentials to the ring electrodes were supplied via a voltage divider chain to ensure a smooth potential slope inside the retarding field unit. Additionally, it was aimed for a more effective shielding with respect to scattered light affecting the detector surface. The grid closer to the detector was constantly held on ground potential (*ground grid*). Any blocking voltage can be applied to the *retarding field grid* between the *ground grid* and *grid 2*.

3.3 Detection and Read out

3.3.1 Microchannel plate detector

For the detection of the electrons, a dual microchannel plate (MCP) detector in Chevron geometry is used (Model: *Hamamatsu F-2223*). It consists of two microchannel plates and an anode. In general, MCPs are designed to detect charged particles (such as electrons or

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.8: (a) Setup with *grid 1* and *grid 2*. (b) Setup with ring electrodes arranged along the axis of the coil.

ions) and photons. Each microchannel plate provides an array of $10^4 - 10^7$ micron-sized, independent electron multipliers (see Fig. 3.9). Typical channel diameters are in the range (10-100) μm and have length-to-diameter ratios between 40 and 100. In order to be de-

tected, charged particles or photons must have a high enough energy to generate free electrons at the front side of the MCP. By applying a positive electric field, the electrons are accelerated through each channel and generate electron cascades. At the anode, a resulting

Figure 3.9: Schematic of an individual miniature electron multiplier membrane capillary of an MCP [18].

electric signal can then be measured. Three voltages are assigned to the detector: one to the front plate (U_F), one to the rear plate (U_R) and one to the anode (U_A). In general, the voltage applied to the front plate of the detector determines whether one detects positively charged ions (negative potential at front plate) or electrons and negatively charged ions (positive potential at front plate). Photons reaching the MCP cannot be influenced by electrical potentials, since they are uncharged. For the purpose of electron detection, the voltages $(U_F, U_R, U_A) = (300, 2100, 2300)$ V have been assigned to the plates. In order to prevent voltage sparks between the plates, the voltages have not been set before a residual gas pressure of 10^{-5} mbar was reached.

As a general rule, the higher the voltages and thus the electric field gradient applied to the MCPs, the more signal gain can be achieved. One can imagine, though, that a very high gain has to be ascribed to an equally high secondary electron generation within the channels. This leads to a temporal decrease in the electric potential, which is needed to accelerate and detect the particles. In fact, the generation of a sufficient amount of electrons will block the individual channel for a short while and therefore prevent the detection of the next particle, which might arrive during that so-called *dead time*, typically in the range of some microseconds. This leads to the fact that a percentage of the actual signal is not detected. As the percentage will rise with increasing signal rates, the MCP detector exhibits a saturation behavior. Further, if all channels are saturated at the same time, the MCP will lose its sensitivity for a few microseconds. The saturation behavior of the MCPs, as well as the decrease in sensitivity in case of a parallel saturation of all channels are, important parts of the measurements.

3.3.2 Multichannel scaler

Figure 3.10: A typical measurement result retrieved from the multichannel scaler.

Signals from the MCP are preamplified by a replica of an *ORTEC VT120* preamp and read out with an *SR430 Multichannel Scaler*. Triggered by a 5 V signal, it counts events as a function of time, averaged over sequential time bins. The bin width can be set from 5 ns to 10 ms, the device then records the number of events in each bin. The displayed graph is a plot of the amount of detected counts against the time, represented by the number of the bin, at which it was detected. A typical measurement result is shown in Fig. 3.10. To obtain a meaningful amount of statistics, the results of several laser pulses are accumulated in one measurement. For the purposes of this thesis, the typical number of considered pulses per measurement is 500, if not stated otherwise. The time of detection can easily be calculated by multiplication of the relevant bin number times the bin width.

Figure 3.11: GAM Laser EX5F 157 nm [19].

3.4 VUV-Excimer-Laser

The laser used in the measurements is a VUV-Excimer-Laser and is shown in Fig. 3.11 (Model: *GAM-Laser EX5F*). The term 'excimer' is a short form of 'excited dimer'. It refers to the laser's functional principle: Usually the gain medium is pumped with short current pulses at high voltages, triggering the generation of metastable excited molecules, which deliver coherent light emission at the moment of decay. In our case, the gain medium is fluorine (F_2) added to helium (He), which acts as a buffer gas, which leads to light emission at a wavelength of 157 nm. The laser's pulse length amounts to 8 ns (T_L) at a maximum energy $E_L = 2$ mJ per pulse and the beam profile is 18 mm^2 [19]. The intensity of the excimer-laser can be calculated following:

$$I = \frac{E_L}{T_L A_L} = \frac{2 \text{ mJ}}{8 \text{ ns} \cdot 18 \text{ mm}^2} = 1.4 \cdot 10^6 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{cm}^2} \quad (3.2)$$

A_L is the area irradiated by the laser pulse and in this context equal to the beam profile. During all measurements, a pulse frequency of 100 Hz has been used. For parts of the measurements, the laser was focused onto the sample by a MgF_2 - lense with a focal length of $f = 5$ cm, shown in Fig. 3.7.

3.5 Electronic Scheme

To get an overview on how all used devices are connected in the experimental setup, an electronic schematic is given in Fig. 3.12.

Figure 3.12: Circuit diagram of the MCP, preamp, multichannel scaler and the Excimer-Laser.

The MCP voltages are applied via independent voltage supplies. The preamplifier used for the setup is a replica of an *ORTEC VT120* [20], connected to a voltage of 12 V. The pre-amplified signal is sent to the multichannel scaler described in Sect. 3.3.2, which is triggered by the excimer laser.

3.6 Vacuum generation and mechanical design

In the experiment, a high vacuum is required for several reasons: To run the MCP detector, a vacuum pressure of 10^{-5} mbar or less has to be generated, in order to prevent sparking between the plates. Moreover, a high vacuum is also mandatory to avoid residual gas ionization by the exciting laser beam and thus creating undesirable background electrons. Therefore, a setup as shown and labeled in Fig. 3.13 was used to generate a pressure of less than 10^{-6} mbar. The cube is pumped by a *Pfeiffer TSU521* turbomolecular drag pumping station (pumping speed 510 l/s for nitrogen N_2) [21]. The pressure is measured with a *Pfeiffer PBR 260* pressure sensor and read out by a *Pfeiffer Vac MaxiGauge* monitoring device [21].

The coil is mounted directly to a DN150CF \rightarrow DN100CF zero length reducer flange (Hositrade [22], Fig. 3.13 (c)). To be able to insert the detector independently of the coil, it is attached with a DN100CF \rightarrow DN40CF zero length reducer flange on top (Hositrade, Fig. 3.13 (b)). The DN150CF extension tube with a length of 333.4 mm and the DN150CF cube

Figure 3.13: Sectional view of the setup with labels of the components: (a) SHV feedthrough: DN40CF, by Allectra. (b) Zero length reducer flange holding the detector: DN100CF \rightarrow DN40CF, by Hositrad. (c) Zero length reducer flange holding the coil, including electrical feedthrough to supply the current for the coil: DN150CF \rightarrow DN100CF, by Hositrad. (d) Extension tube: DN150CF, length: 333.4 mm, by Hositrad. (e) Cube: DN150CF, by Hositrad.

(both Hositrad, Fig. 3.13 (e),(f)) give space for the inner components of the experiment. The DN40CF flange on top of the system by Allectra [23] is custom-made design manufactured including four separate SHV feedthroughs (Fig. 3.13 (a)).

In order to mount the sample, the permanent magnet and the lense, a base plate with threaded holes is attached to the inside of the cube.

4 Measurements and results

4.1 Measurement goals

In this thesis it was probed if conditions can be achieved that allow for a significant suppression of photoelectrons, as emitted during the laser irradiation of a sample surface. This suppression should be sufficiently large to allow for the detection of IC electrons, emitted within $7 \mu\text{s}$ half-life during the decay of $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ following an individual laser pulse of 5 ns duration. For the purpose of the detection of IC electrons, it is important to understand how the spectrometer signal reacts to the different applied voltages. As stated in Sect. 3.3.2, the obtained signal corresponds to the amount of counts as a function of the time of arrival at the MCP. According to [12], the neutral isomer of ^{229}Th has a half life of $7 \pm 1 \mu\text{s}$ in the IC decay channel. For the detection of the IC electrons, most of the background within the spectrometer must be suppressed after the impact of the laser pulse, to allow to retrieve an exponentially decreasing signal originating from the isomeric decay. In this case, the signal can unambiguously be identified as originating from IC electrons.

For most measurements, the setup discussed in Chap. 3 was used and will from now on be assumed standard, if not stated otherwise. Once a pressure of 10^{-5} mbar was reached, the MCP voltages were applied. After assigning voltages to the grids and the sample and switching on the coil current, the VUV laser was started. For some of the measurements, the pressure sensor was used as a source of constant electronic background, as required to probe the MCP detector sensitivity.

4.2 Influence of the grids

Laser-irradiation of the surfaces within the setup will lead to photoelectron emission within the system. In particular, photoelectrons are expected to emerge from the sample surface, on which the laser is focused, as from all surfaces affected by scattered light, such as the

Figure 4.1: Top: Potential curve corresponding to the measurement in Fig. 4.2: The red curve corresponds to Fig. 4.2 (a), the blue one to Fig. 4.2 (b). Bottom: Scheme of the setup segmented in three regions: (1) Volume of the cube including the sample and the permanent magnet. (2) Volume inside the coil margined by *grid 1* and *grid 2*. (3) Volume between *grid 1* and the MCP detector.

grids, the coil body and the detector's surface. These electrons are then guided towards the MCP within the coil body by the magnetic mirror (Sect. 2.2) and compose a background, drowning a possibly occurring IC decay. In this section it is probed, how assigning different potentials to the grids and the sample affects these electrons and if they can possibly be suppressed. To illustrate the measurement, a scheme is shown in Fig. 4.1, including a potential curve. For simplicity reasons, the inside of the spectrometer is divided in three regions, as indicated by the numbers in Fig. 4.1.

One can imagine that photoelectrons emerging directly from the MCP's surface and in region (3) (see Fig. 4.1) will not be affected by voltages assigned to grids in front of the detector and hence be unsuppressable. On the other hand, these electrons emerge closer to the detector

Figure 4.2: Changing signal at varying voltages of *grid 2*.

than all others and will therefore be detected first.

In a measurement series it was tested how to manipulate the obtained signal and identify certain peaks with certain areas of electron emission. In order to prevent saturation of the detector, lower voltages compared to the standard values from Sect. 3.3.1 were assigned to the MCP as follows: $(U_F, U_R, U_A) = (300, 1600, 1850)$. To avoid photoelectron emission from the sample, the sample was set to a fixed potential of +15 V. *Grid 1* was set to -60 V and the *grid 2* voltage was varied as stated in Fig. 4.2 (only two exemplaric signals are shown, with values of ± 3 V relative to the voltage of *grid 1*).

The expectation for this measurement is, that all photoelectrons to be detected must exceed the *grid 1* potential of -60 V and thus have a kinetic energy of at least 60 eV. Therefore the *grid 2* potential was varied around -60 V. For absolute potential values larger than 60 V, a stronger signal was expected, as the electrons should have a kinetic energy larger than 60 eV, following $E_{kin,electric} = q\phi$ (q : electric charge and ϕ : electric potential). By analogy, for *grid 2* absolute potential values smaller than 60 eV, a suppression of (parts of) the signal is expected. It is nicely visible in Fig. 4.2 that a tremendous reduction of counts occurs for *grid 2* absolute potential values smaller than the 60 V blocking potential. The first two signal peaks arriving right before 1 μs were not affected by changes in neither the *grid 2* nor the sample voltages. It can be concluded that these counts do not arise from photoelectrons created in regions (1) and (2), as displayed in Fig. 4.1. This supports the prediction made about the unsuppressability of photoelectrons emerging in region (3). Moreover, these peaks are

Figure 4.3: Changing signal at varying voltages of *grid 2* and repelling sample voltage of -15 V.

the earliest signals to be detected, which underlines this theory, as the laser photons reach the detector surface with speed of light and thus arrive earliest. In Figs. 4.2 (a) and 4.3 (a), many peaks are detected between 1 and 2 μs , exhibiting decreasing count rates and an oscillation pattern. Their origin can be ascribed to reflections within the magnetic bottle: Electrons leave from *grid 1* and can exceed the potential barrier. This leads to the constant signal background detected before the actual laser pulse, which originates from the pressure sensor, that was not switched off for these measurements.

To undermine the interpretation, subsequently the sample voltage was switched to -15 V, repelling instead of attracting photoelectrons emerging from the sample and accelerating them towards the MCP. Repeating the, apart from that, unchanged measurement was expected to yield an unchanged signal, as also the sample electrons should not have enough energy to exceed the blocking potential of *grid 1*.

Fig. 4.3 shows a very similar distribution of counts as Fig. 4.2 and thus proves that no additional counts originating from the sample were detected, which underlines that a certain part of the signal can be shielded. This also leads to the conclusion that electrons detected at a negative *grid 2* potential originate from spectrometer region (3) and hence should be suppressable by appropriate voltage parameters.

4.3 Reduced MCP sensitivities

For the measurements presented in Sect. 4.2 a total time period of $5 \mu\text{s}$ was examined. A signal influence by changing setup parameters was obviously possible. Two types of measurements at a total time period of $60 \mu\text{s}$ are shown in Fig. 4.4. Fig. 4.4 (a) shows a measurement with switched off pressure sensor and Fig. 4.4 (b) presents the same measurement, however, with switched on pressure sensor. In both cases a large peak occurs due to photoelectrons within the first $5 \mu\text{s}$. In Fig. 4.4 (a) the background after the first peak nearly disappears. A comparison to the measurement shown in Fig. 4.4 (b) exhibits a strong increase of counts between 20 to $30 \mu\text{s}$ and a resulting constant, far from negligible background. As the pressure sensor should constantly deliver electrons by residual gas ionization, a constant background as occurring after $\sim 30 \mu\text{s}$ would be expected over the whole measurement period. It can be concluded that after the first peak, originating from photoelectrons, the sensitivity of the detector is drastically reduced for about $30 \mu\text{s}$. Hence the MCP does not detect all appearing counts in this time period. As the $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ IC decay channel has a half-life of $7 \pm 1 \mu\text{s}$, the conversion electrons are expected to appear predominantly exactly during this time period. For this reason, the reduced sensitivity of the MCP after the laser pulse poses a problem for the isomer detection concept, which has to be addressed.

This measurement was performed in a modified setup (see Sect. 3.2.2) with the retarding fields applied in accordance with Fig. 4.5. No voltages were assigned to *grid 2* and the *retarding field grid*, the sample was set onto -20 V . The MCP plates were set to $(U_F, U_R, U_A) = (300, 2050, 2300) \text{ V}$ from the front plate to the anode.

Taking a closer look at the same measurement in an enlarged picture, it is apparent that in the time period of saturation, the detector is not fully 'blind', but rather has a drastically reduced detection efficiency (see Sect. 4.5). Comparison of Figs. 4.6 (a) and 4.6 (b) yields, that from the very moment on when the detection efficiency rises again (at $\sim 7 \mu\text{s}$), a background signal is detected, which exhibits a slow reduction on a longer time scale. As the sample is set to a repellant potential, these counts are clearly originating from the sample. An explanation for the exponential distribution might be thermionic electron emission as a result of the laser surface heating.

To investigate the detector sensitivity for different laser intensities, an aperture with 1 mm diameter was placed in front of the laser to reduce the laser power effectively when irradiating the sample. The measurement at a retarding field voltage of -10 V , a sample voltage of

Figure 4.4: (a) Measurement with switched off pressure sensor. (b) Measurement with switched on pressure sensor exhibiting a drastic reduction in detection sensitivity after the laser pulse.

-20 V and a switched-off pressure sensor did not remove the sensitivity reduction following the laser pulse, but the signal most likely originating from thermionic electrons was reduced (Fig. 4.7 (a)). For a subsequent measurement, a $150 \mu\text{m}$ diameter aperture was inserted. At a sample voltage of -20 V without retarding field and switched on pressure sensor, the detector was exhibiting only minor sensitivity reduction (Fig. 4.7 (b)).

Only in case of a drastical reduction in laser intensity, the problem of reduced MCP sensitivity was solved. As this reduction of laser intensity would also lead to a reduced nuclear excitation rate, a different way of solution had to be investigated.

4.4 Saturation behavior

Besides the sensitivity loss following the photoelectron peak, the MCP detection system also exhibits a saturation behavior. During the maximum peak intensities, the MCP is unable to count each individual electron, leading to a saturation of the detector. Further, the discriminator built into the multichannel scaler (see Sect. 3.3.2) will show zero signal in case, that a

Figure 4.5: Scheme of the modified setup with its potential curve corresponding to Sect. 4.3.

Figure 4.6: (a) Exponential decrease of the signal after the laser pulse with the pressure sensor switched off. (b) Decreased detector sensitivity after the laser pulse with pressure sensor switched on.

Figure 4.7: Inserted apertures reducing the power of the laser: (a) A 1mm diameter aperture suppresses thermionic electrons. (b) 150 μm aperture and switched-on pressure sensor reduce the saturation the detector.

certain count-rate limit is exceeded.

Figure 4.8: (a) Signal at low detector sensitivity (b) Signal at increased detector sensitivity (c) Signal at optimum MCP parameters. (d) Signal at reversed magnetic field suppressing sample electrons.

In order to investigate the saturation behavior of the detector, the MCP front plate was set to a potential of $U_F = 300$ V and varying voltages U_R and U_A were applied to the rear plate and the anode as stated in Fig. 4.8. 500 pulses at a bin length of 5 ns, a retarding field of -10 V and a sample voltage of -20 V were studied. Fig. 4.8 (a) shows the obtained signals at a low MCP voltage gradient as stated in the figure. Only one peak is detected, originating from sample photoelectrons. The obtained signal intensity increases for increasing detector voltages and for voltage setups as indicated in Fig. 4.8 (b) on, four peaks arise. The additional peaks compared to Fig. 4.8 (a) likely originate from the inside of the spectrometer and from photoelectrons emerging at the detector surface. Also reflections of sample electrons within the coil can be thought of, leading to deferred signals. In Fig. 4.8 (c), a saturation of the MCP is occurring at the split-up of the peak after $1 \mu\text{s}$. For the measurement shown in Fig. 4.8 (d), the magnetic field of the coil was reversed. Therefore no magnetic mirror effect was present and thus less sample electrons were expected. As the recorded amount of counts is significantly reduced compared to Fig. 4.8 (c) at identical MCP settings but reversed magnetic field, it can be concluded that the missing part of the signal originates from the sample. Electrons emerging from within the spectrometer, apart from the sample, are not expected

Figure 4.9: Sketch of the setup with potential curve to probe the sample electron suppression.

to be affected by the magnetic mirror effect and would hence explain the residual detected electrons in Fig. 4.8 (d).

During the next step it had to be tested if a positive sample voltage can serve to hold the electrons on the surface. In the case of success, a triggered sample voltage could serve to withhold all sample photoelectrons from emission at the time of laser irradiation. In order to prevent saturation, the MCP parameters were set to $(U_F, U_R, U_A) = (300, 1500, 1700)$ V. A retarding field voltage of -10 V was applied and the sample was set to -15 V and 0 V, according to Fig. 4.9.

Fig. 4.10 shows the results of this measurement. In case (a), which corresponds to a sample voltage of -15 V, the sample electrons have enough energy to exceed the retarding field

Figure 4.10: (a) A sample voltage of -15 V provides the electrons with enough energy to exceed the retarding field potential of -10 V and leads to a peak after $1 \mu\text{s}$. (b) Switching off the sample voltage leads to a vanishing of the peak and thus to successful sample photoelectron suppression.

of -10 V and are detected after $1 \mu\text{s}$. Switching off the sample voltage, as shown in Fig. 4.10 (b), leads to a vanishing of the peak, hence the sample electrons were successfully suppressed.

4.5 Triggered sample voltage

As was given proof in the previous section, the occurrence of sample photoelectrons can be avoided by a switched-off or positive sample voltage. It remains to be probed if a suppression of the sample photoelectrons results in a solution of the problem of reduced MCP sensitivity after the laser pulse and if the same also holds for a triggered sample potential. For a nuclear laser excitation experiment a triggered sample voltage on the sample would not only suppress the photoelectrons, but also the IC electrons originating from the isomeric decay. In order to probe these aspects, the pressure sensor was turned on and a voltage of $+20 \text{ V}$ and respectively -20 V was assigned to the sample. A 1 mm diameter aperture was placed in front of the laser and the MCP voltages were applied, as stated in Sect. 3.3.1. Signals corresponding to Fig. 4.11 (a) and (b) were obtained.

Figure 4.11: (a) Signal at -20 V sample voltage with switched on pressure sensor exhibiting a distinct detector sensitivity reduction after the laser pulse. (b) Switching the sample voltage to $+20$ V avoids the sensitivity reduction after the laser pulse and affects the background.

In Fig. 4.11 (a) a distinct reduction of the detector sensitivity is visible, as expected. Setting the sample onto a potential of $+20$ V in Fig. 4.11 (b) significantly reduces the whole signal. Sensitivity reduction no longer occurs, however, the constant pressure sensor background is also affected.

It remains to be tested if setting the sample to a triggered positive voltage would still solve the problem of the MCP sensitivity reduction. Therefore, the sample was connected to a function generator setting the sample onto a positive potential of $+5$ V during the laser irradiation, aiming to avoid photoelectron emission. A few μs after the laser pulse, a constant potential of -5 V was applied to the sample, thereby also allowing for the detection of sample electrons. At standard MCP voltages of $(U_F, U_R, U_A) = (300, 2100, 2300)$ V and turned off grid voltages, respectively, 500 pulses have been examined at switched-on pressure sensor, as will be detailed in the following.

In Fig. 4.12 (a), a reference measurement with a constant sample voltage of -5 V was performed. By analogy to earlier measurements (Sect. 4.3) and thus expected, the detector exhibits reduced sensitivity after the impact of the laser pulse and recovers after ~ 20 μs . For the measurement in Fig. 4.12 (b), the sample was set onto a positive voltage of $+5$ V for 5 μs , and was then nearly instantaneously switched to -5 V. A distinct decrease of photoelec-

Figure 4.12: Saturation measurements at triggered sample voltages. (a) Reference measurement with a constant sample voltage of -5 V. (b) Signal with trigger-switched sample voltage after $5 \mu\text{s}$. (c) Signal with trigger-switched sample voltage after $1 \mu\text{s}$.

trons is visible, but it is even more remarkable that no sensitivity reduction seems to occur. During the $5 \mu\text{s}$ of a positive sample voltage, a decreased count rate can be observed. In the moment of switching the sample voltage, the count rate increases nearly immediately to the constant count level provided by the pressure sensor. As previously shown, the pressure sensor background signal is affected by the sample voltage and consequently the constant background of the pressure sensor is reduced during the first $5 \mu\text{s}$. The measurement in Fig. 4.12 (c) supports this interpretation: Here, nearly the same measurement was performed, just the time of the voltage reversion was shortened on $1 \mu\text{s}$. No reduction of the background count rate is observed and it can thus be concluded that the short duration of the positive sample potential suffices to capture all emerging sample photoelectrons that led to a reduced MCP sensitivity as seen before.

As proven by the measurements shown in Fig. 4.12, saturation-free sensitivity for electron detection can be obtained. In a subsequent measurement using the same voltage settings for the MCP, a total of 32765 pulses were examined during $20 \mu\text{s}$ acquisition time (preset: 50000 pulses, but the measurement stopped automatically). A trigger-induced sample voltage change from $+5$ V to -5 V after $1 \mu\text{s}$ was applied and the pressure sensor was switched off. The retarding field potential was set to -3 V in order to repel electrons emerging from the spectrometer region. Further, a 1 mm diameter aperture was inserted in front of the laser and the lense was removed from the inside of the spectrometer. To guarantee full laser power,

Figure 4.13: Count rate at a triggered sample voltage without constant background generated by the pressure sensor.

the exit of the laser was floated with nitrogen, in order to prevent absorption of the VUV light by the air. The obtained signal can be seen in Fig. 4.13.

Although after $\sim 6 \mu\text{s}$ a nearly background-free signal seems to be obtained, which is very promising for further measurements, there is a remaining signal between 2 and 6 μs after the laser pulse. This signal could potentially be a source of background for the detection of the isomeric decay, due to the IC decay half-life of 7 μs . By variation of the sample voltage, it was possible to show that these electrons are emitted from the sample. It remains to be clarified, however, what the origin of these background counts is and if the suppression of the background signal is already sufficient for a detection of IC electrons.

In order to answer the last question, it shall be estimated what signal-to-background ratio can be expected for the nuclear laser excitation scheme proposed in [11], in case that no further reduction in background rate can be achieved.

For this estimate, it is important to note that the peak intensity of the excimer laser is about $1.4 \cdot 10^6 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{cm}^2}$ and thus slightly larger than that of the tunable laser system which will be employed for the nuclear excitation ($2 \cdot 10^5 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{cm}^2}$) [11]. For this reason, the observed number of background electrons can serve as an upper bound for the ultimately expected number of

Figure 4.14: Measured number of background electrons (red), compared to expected number of IC electrons in resonance (blue) for 32765 pulses at 40 ns bin width [11].

electrons in the experiment.

As one can expect about 4200 excited nuclei per pulse [11], the number of $3.27 \cdot 10^4$ laser pulses corresponds to a total number of $N_{tot} = 1.3 \cdot 10^8$ excited nuclei. Assuming, that a measurement is started $5 \mu\text{s}$ after the laser pulse and stopped $10 \mu\text{s}$ after the laser pulse, there would be

$$N = N_{tot}[\exp^{-\frac{1}{2}} - \exp^{-1}] = 0.24N_{tot} = 3.1 \cdot 10^7 \quad (4.1)$$

expected isomeric decays, where the $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ lifetime of $10 \mu\text{s}$ was used. This has to be compared to a number of background counts of 831 in the same time interval, thus leading to a signal-to-background ratio caused by the laser induced background of $3.7 \cdot 10^4$. Thus, the IC electrons are expected to dominate the signal and hence, the suppression of the background electrons by the triggered sample voltage seems sufficient. The expected signal-to-background ratio is plotted in Fig. 4.14.

To readdress the question for the origin of the unsuppressable background signal, however,

we see three potential explanations. These are: (1) An afterglow of the laser pulse, leading to delayed photoelectron emission from the sample surface. (2) Thermionic electron emission. This is, however, unlikely as the laser intensity should not suffice to increase the surface temperature notably. (3) Trapping of electrons in the magnetic field of the permanent magnet, as long as the sample voltage is set on a positive potential.

Further investigations will be required in order to determine the source of background. Ideally, these should be performed with the same tunable laser source that will later be used for isomeric excitation (see Sect. 2.3).

5 Conclusion and outlook

The major objective of this Bachelor's thesis was to provide a close-to background-free measurement environment to pave the way for a direct laser excitation of the isomeric state as proposed in [11], which would automatically lead to a drastical reduction of the uncertainty of the isomeric energy value. The idea of this concept is to probe the IC decay of the isomeric state, following the direct laser excitation of $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ in a solid sample. For this purpose a magnetic bottle spectrometer has been constructed, utilizing the magnetic mirror effect to guide the electrons onto an MCP detector. Also an energy measurement by a retarding field, implementing a tunable blocking voltage in the spectrometer is feasible with the setup.

In order to probe the electron background signal, that has to be expected after the laser pulse, used for isomer excitation, a VUV excimer laser providing a wavelength of 157 nm and 8 ns pulse duration was used to irradiate a sample. The impact of the laser pulse on the surfaces, however, leads to photoelectron emission. A multitude of measurements were performed in order to understand and reduce the background caused by photoelectron emission. Successful reduction of the background was achieved by applying voltages to the retarding field grids and the sample.

A reduced detection sensitivity of the detector was discovered by performing long term measurements with switched on and switched off pressure sensors, providing a constant background count rate, due to residual gas ionization. From the measurements in Sect. 4.4, it can be inferred, that the dominating part of the photoelectrons emerges from the sample. In order to solve the problems of a reduced MCP sensitivity and a high background rate, a triggered sample voltage was applied. A suppression of the photoelectrons was achieved: during laser irradiation, the sample was set to a voltage of +5 V, hindering the photoelectrons from leaving the sample surface. In this way, nearly the whole background could be suppressed, except for the counts generated by photoelectrons emerging from the detector surface and a small but non-negligible amount of counts registered after ~ 2 to $4 \mu\text{s}$. It is uncertain of which origin these electrons are. The origin might be an after glow of the laser pulse, leading to photoelectron emission after the sample was reset to a negative voltage. Another possibility might be an interaction between the electrons emerging at the sample and the magnetic field of the permanent magnet, resulting in a delayed release after the laser

pulse has terminated.

In conclusion, a nearly background free measurement environment was realized, which bears the potential for promising attempts for the isomeric laser excitation and measurements of the transition energy. In particular, the measurements concerning the reduction in MCP sensitivity owed to the high laser intensity gave valuable insights on how to deal with MCP detectors in combination with background photoelectrons. In a next step, the setup should be tested with the laser system that is planned to be used for isomeric excitation. This system is currently in preparation.

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